

Diagnostic Findings in Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia (CLL): Peripheral Blood Smear, Bone Marrow Aspiration, Iron Storage, and Immunophenotype

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Abstract:

Background: One of the most prevalent forms of adult leukemia is chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL), which can proceed in a variety of ways and present with a wide range of signs and symptoms. In this study, we looked into the correlation and frequency of laboratory results for CLL patients, such as cellular Immunophenotyping, bone marrow aspiration and biopsy, and peripheral blood smear.

Methods: All 161 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of CLL had their laboratory data retrieved for this cross-sectional, retrospective analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to assess the frequency and correlation between various laboratory parameters. Techniques with the Jamovi software update (2022).

Results: 161 individuals had their laboratory and demographic characteristics, including thrombocytopenia, anaemia, white blood cell count, lymphocyte percentage, and patterns of bone marrow involvement, assessed. There was a substantial correlation between the percentage of atypical lymphocytes in peripheral blood and the percentage of FMC7 marker expression in the bone marrow.

Conclusion: A variety of diagnostic methods can be used to identify chronic lymphocytic leukaemia, a common kind of leukaemia linked to significant death and morbidity. Examining the frequency of certain diagnostic tests and analysing their findings these symptoms in those who have the illness can be very helpful for an early diagnosis and prognosis assessment in those who are affected.

Keywords: Bone Marrow Cells, Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia, Lymphocyte Immunophenotyping.

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Introduction

Especially in Western nations, chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) is one of the most common forms of leukemia. The accumulation of mature B lymphocytes in the blood, lymph nodes, spleen, liver, and bone marrow are a characteristic of this disease, which is classified as a clonal lymphoid malignancy [1-3].

The illness primarily affects men and the elderly [4]. Studies show that almost 30% of leukemia cases worldwide are caused by chronic lymphocytic leukemia [5]. There are currently no accurate records pertaining to the incidence of CLL in Iran. Nevertheless, it can be deduced from the data that chronic lymphocytic leukemia is a common type of blood cancer in Iran, along with acute lymphocytic leukemia, acute myeloid leukemia, and multiple myeloma. All leukaemia together account for about 8% of recognized around the nation. [6-8] When a person is diagnosed with chronic lymphocytic leukemia, their clinical symptoms can vary widely. These

days, the expanding. The early diagnosis of this illness has been made possible by the increased demand for complete blood cell count (CBC) tests. Therefore, the early phases of this condition (the early stages of the Rai and Binet categorization system, which is detailed below) account for almost 70% of patient diagnoses. Though the disease progresses differently in these people, roughly 30–40% of them have rapid disease progression and clinical symptoms [9,10].

There are several ways to assess the prognosis of chronic lymphocytic leukemia; the Rai and Binet approaches are among the most well-known. Categorization scheme. This technique is dependent on clinical factors such as complete blood counts (CBCs), physical exams, and the number of organs implicated. The Rai system comprises five levels (0 to IV), while the Binet system consists of three levels: A, B, and C. Additionally, there is a modified Rai system that features three risk levels— low, intermediate, and

high. These correspond to levels 0 and combinations of Level I and II, as well as a combination of Level

III and IV from the Rai classification system (Table 1) [11,12].

Table 1: Rai and Binet system for CLL classification

Rai stage		Binet stage	
0-	Lymphocytosis only	A	<3 Lymphadenopathies plus Lymphocytosis
I-	Stage 0 plus Lymphadenopathy	B	≥3 Lymphadenopathies plus Lymphocytosis
II-	Stage 0 plus Splenomegaly or hepatomegaly		
III-	Stage 0 plus Anemia (hemoglobin <11 g/dL)	C	As for stage A or B Hemoglobin <10g/dL and/or platelet count <100 × 10 ⁹ /L
IV-	Stage 0 plus Thrombocytopenia (platelet count <100 × 10 ⁹ /L)		

Various laboratory assessments have been proposed for diagnosing chronic lymphocytic leukemia. These methods encompass the complete blood cell count test (CBC), peripheral blood smear (PBS), flow cytometry (cell immunophenotyping), bone marrow aspiration and biopsy (BMA/B), cytogenetic tests, fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH) test, molecular tests, lymph node biopsy, spinal tap, and other diagnostic procedures. Among

these, peripheral blood smear and cellular immunophenotyping hold greater significance. [13]

Peripheral blood smears: The first and most important change that occurs in patients with CLL is lymphocytosis in the peripheral blood and bone marrow. Classic 'smudge cells' or 'basket cells' are also observed in the peripheral blood smear. [14] (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Presence of atypical lymphocytes, polymphocytes, and smudge cells in peripheral blood smear (Giemsa, 400X magnification)

In the 5th edition of the WHO classification of hematolymphoid tumors, the family of pre-neoplastic and neoplastic small lymphocytic proliferations under the section of mature B-cell neoplasms consists of two entities: Monoclonal B-cell Lymphocytosis (MBL) and Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia/Small lymphocytic Lymphoma (CLL/SLL) which remains the same and the category of 'B-prolymphocytic leukemia' (B-PLL) is no longer used, as it includes a heterogeneous group of hematolymphoid neoplasms. [15]

Within the MBL group, there is a subtype of CLL/SLL-type MBL that lacks any additional CLL/SLL traits and has a monoclonal CLL/SLL-phenotype B-cell count of less than 0.5 × 10⁹/L and

a total B-cell count of less than 5 × 10⁹/L. Patients with a peripheral blood polymphocyte percentage between 11 and 55% have a different group of patients with a disease comparable to CLL; this illness is known as CLL/PLL (prolymphocytic leukemia). A diagnosis of PLL is made if the polymphocyte percentage is more than 55%. [16]

The subsequent categorization pertains to individuals whose peripheral blood atypical lymphocyte proportion (lymphoplasmacytic and cleaved cells) above 10%. These patients are classified as Atypical CLL, a subtype of hematolymphoid malignancies excluded from the WHO's 5th edition. (17) There is substantial evidence linking the kind of CLL, clinical

symptoms, and prognosis. Compared to individuals with typical CLL, patients with atypical cell morphology CLL (both CLL/PLL and Atypical CLL) have a worse prognosis and experience a slower course of the disease. [16,18] Complete blood count (CBC): A high white blood cell (WBC) count with lymphocyte predominance is often a common finding in this test. Thrombocytopenia and anaemia are two other significant results of this test. If they are there, they show how the illness is progressing. [19]

Flow Cytometry and Immunophenotyping

These diagnostic tests are used to evaluate the individual cell types implicated and confirm the diagnosis of CLL and determine the disease prognosis. The typical CLL phenotype often includes being CD5 (+), CD19(+), CD20(+), CD23(+), FMC7(-), with weak expression of surface Ig (sIg), and weak expression or absence of membrane CD22. [4, 14, 21-23]

The timely diagnosis of the illness can be substantially aided by evaluating the outcomes of various diagnostic tests and looking into the prevalence of these findings among patients. Consequently, this improves the therapeutic process and lowers the patients' rates of death and morbidity. Thus, we have attempted to investigate the frequency and meaning of results from bone marrow aspirations and biopsies, immunophenotyping, peripheral blood smears, and assessments of iron storage in patients with chronic lymphocytic leukemia in this study.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional, retrospective epidemiological study included all patients (161) referred to the hematopathology between April 2023 and Jan 2024 and diagnosed with chronic lymphocytic leukaemia. Clinical history, physical examination, peripheral blood smear, complete blood cell count, bone marrow biopsy and aspiration, immunophenotypic criteria, and a monoclonal B lymphocyte count $\geq 5 \times 10^9/L$ were used to establish the diagnosis in accordance with the guidelines of the IWCLL (International Workshop on Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia), which is the same as the WHO classification of haematolymphoid tumours.

While atypical CLL is not included in the 5th edition of the WHO classification, our study categorized patients into two groups—typical and atypical chronic lymphocytic leukemia and compared various factors between these two groups—due to its retrospective nature. This decision was also prompted by Robak et al., who discussed atypical CLL in their study despite explaining the exclusion of the atypical category in the last version of the WHO classification [17]. The classification was determined by the presence of atypical lymphocytes

exceeding 10%, prolymphocytes exceeding 10%, or the expression of markers FMC7 exceeding 20%, CD23 below 20%, CD5/19 below 20%, and instances of CD20 bright expression, which were considered indicative of Atypical CLL cases. A comparative analysis was conducted between the two groups, examining bone marrow involvement patterns, bone marrow iron storage, and marker expression.

Inclusion Criteria

Confirmation of CLL diagnosis through clinical history, physical examination, complete blood count, peripheral blood slide, bone marrow biopsy and aspiration, immunophenotypic criteria, and a B lymphocyte count $\geq 5 \times 10^9/L$.

Inclusion of newly diagnosed CLL cases that have not received prior CLL treatment. Availability of patient's diagnostic test information, including peripheral blood smear report, complete blood cell count, bone marrow aspiration and biopsy report, and Immunophenotyping report of the disease.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients without a definitive diagnosis of CLL will be excluded from the study.
- Patients with other B and T lymphoid neoplasms were also excluded from the study.

The study was retrospective, and information related to it was extracted from the flow cytometry and pathology sheets of patients available in the hematopathology laboratory of Afzalipur Hospital. However, due to the incomplete availability of information in the main patients' files in the hospital archive regarding patients' history and physical examinations, and considering that some patients were diagnosed with Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia (CLL) on an outpatient basis; our access to certain details was limited. Consequently, information such as the presence of lymphadenopathy, and organomegaly was not included in this study. Furthermore, since the patients included in this study were newly diagnosed cases of CLL and due to the retrospective cross-sectional nature of the study, no follow-up evaluations for Richter's transformation were conducted.

Data collection was carried out using a registration form that encompassed various components. This form included demographic information of patients, comprising age and gender. Furthermore, it gathered information from peripheral blood smear examinations, covering the assessment of red blood cells, their morphology, and white blood cells along with their differential and count, as well as platelets.

Additionally, it encompassed data acquired from biopsies and bone marrow aspirations, involving the categorization of factors such as cellularity,

bone marrow involvement pattern, bone marrow iron storage, and bone marrow cellularity. Lastly, the immunophenotypic details of lymphocytes were also documented. All these aspects were meticulously extracted for each patient from pathology and flow cytometry reports.

The accumulated data were then encoded into an Excel file for subsequent analysis and review.

Results

In the descriptive findings section, the results are as follows: Among the 161 patients with CLL, 93 individuals were in the Atypical CLL category, and 68 individuals were in the Typical CLL category. Out of the 161 patients with CLL, 50 were female, and 111 were male. Among the 158 patients with

CLL at the time of diagnosis, 94 had anemia, while 64 did not have anemia. Of the 160 patients with CLL, 31 had thrombocytopenia at the time of diagnosis, and 129 had normal platelets. The number of patients with CLL was 7, 27, 37, 35, 19, and 6, categorized according to the degree of iron storage from grade 0 to 5 (Figure 2).

The frequency of patients for each pattern of bone marrow involvement was as follows: 26 had the interstitial pattern, 8 had the focal pattern, 75 had the diffuse pattern, 21 had the nodular pattern, 12 had the interstitial & nodular pattern, and 17 had the interstitial & focal pattern (Figure 3) (Up to 161 patients, the remaining number of patients had missing data). Other descriptive results are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of descriptive results of various analyzed factors

	Mean	Median	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Age	63.8	64	10.8	30	89
WBC count	50928	30000	61371	6300	500000
Lymphocyte percent	55.9	62	28.2	0	100
Lymphocyte count	27628	14040	39716	0	277200
Atypical lymphocyte (%)	20.4	11	24.5	0	85
Prolymphocyte (%)	3.33	0	5.23	0	25
Platelet count	140101	130000	70703	10200	340000
FCM/CD19 expression (%)	57	57	20.5	7	95
FCM/CD19&CD5 co-expression	43.6	41.1	18.4	14	94
FCM/CD22 expression (%)	32.6	30.7	23	0.1	91.8
FCM/CD20 expression (%)	52.1	49.3	20.8	9	100
FCM/CD23 expression (%)	47.7	52	20.7	0.36	93
FCM/FMC7 expression (%)	6.85	4	12.2	0.02	100

Figure 2: Bone marrow iron storage (grade 3) (Prussian blue, 400X magnification)

In the analytical results section, we examined the relationship between various factors. While evaluating the correlation between the percentage of prolymphocytes and 6 cell markers including

CD19, CD19&CD5 co-expression, CD20, CD22, CD23, and FMC7 no significant relationship was found (P>0.05). During the analysis, a significant relationship was observed between the percentage

of atypical lymphocytes and the percentage of expression of cellular markers. An inverse relationship was identified between the expression of the FMC7 marker and the percentage of atypical lymphocytes ($P=0.006$). Furthermore, a weaker yet still significant direct relationship was found with CD19 ($P=0.039$), CD20 ($P=0.021$), and an inverse relationship with CD22 ($P=0.032$). During the analysis of the relationship between CLL type and bone marrow involvement pattern, no significant correlation was discovered ($P>0.05$).

According to the results of the statistical analysis, a significant inverse relationship was found between the degree of bone marrow iron storage and the percentage of atypical lymphocytes ($P<0.001$). This indicates that as the percentage of atypical lymphocytes increases in peripheral blood among CLL patients, their bone marrow iron storage level decreases.

Based on the results of the statistical analysis, no significant correlation was observed between the type of CLL (typical/atypical), the WBC count, the percentage of prolymphocytes and lymphocytes in peripheral blood, thrombocytopenia and anemia with the degree of iron storage in bone marrow aspiration ($P>0.05$). Regarding the results of the statistical test, no significant relationship was found between anemia and the bone marrow involvement pattern ($P>0.05$). Similarly, the correlation between leukocytosis and thrombocytopenia with the pattern of bone marrow involvement was not statistically significant ($P>0.05$).

Finally, according to the outcomes of the statistical analysis, the mean percentage of CD22 and FMC7 marker expression on lymphocytes from individuals diagnosed with atypical CLL exhibited a higher value, although this difference lacked statistical significance. In contrast, the mean expression of CD23 on lymphocytes from those with typical CLL was notably elevated, showing a significant distinction ($P=0.045$). Regarding the remaining markers, no noteworthy correlation was detected.

Discussion

A lymphoproliferative condition known as chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL) causes mature, tiny B lymphocytes to be dispersed throughout the bone marrow, blood, and occasionally lymph nodes. Small lymphocytic lymphoma, or SLL, is the name given to the condition when it affects lymph nodes with or without bone marrow involvement. Neoplastic lymphocytes in these two disorders express the surface markers CD5 and CD23, and they also express lower levels of CD10, FMC7, and CD79b. [24] CLL/SLL is the most common type of leukemia in Western countries, affecting mostly elderly individuals and being rare in those under the age of 30. The ratio of men to women in this disease is 2:1, and the genetic sequence plays a role

in its occurrence, with a probability that is 8 times higher in first-degree relatives [25]. In this study, 161 patients were enrolled with a definitive diagnosis of CLL, out of which 111 were male patients and 50 were female, resulting in a ratio of 2.2/1. This ratio is closely aligned with the findings of most studies. Specifically, Marzieh Bagheri's study reported a ratio of 2.1/1 [26], while Basabaeen's study reported a ratio of 2.5/1 [27].

The average age of the population was 63.8 ± 10.8 , with a median of 64 years. The age range at the time of diagnosis varied from a minimum of 30 to a maximum of 89 years. This is in comparison to the findings of Bagheri's study, which reported an average age of 64.34 (26), Payandeh's study with an average of 60.73 [28], and Basabaeen's study with an average of 62.97 ± 12.06 (27).

Regarding the level of iron storage in the bone marrow, graded from 0 to 5, among the 131 patients for whom iron levels could be measured, the distribution of CLL patients according to the iron storage grades was as follows: grade 0 (7 patients), grade 1 (27 patients), grade 2 (37 patients), grade 3 (35 patients), grade 4 (19 patients), and grade 5 (6 patients). The discussion on evaluating bone marrow iron storage and its relationship with leukemias, including CLL, is a relatively new topic, and there have been limited similar studies conducted both within and outside of Iran. However, in a study conducted by Marjan Abedi on pediatric patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL), the impact of iron content in bone marrow cells on their resistance to methotrexate treatment was examined. The study found that higher levels of iron in bone marrow cells correlated with increased resistance to methotrexate treatment. Consequently, elevated levels of iron in the body and bone marrow could potentially act as a factor against successful methotrexate treatment, potentially leading to disease relapse following treatment [29].

In the present study, the average white blood cell count was $50,928\pm 61,371$ per microliter, with a median of 30,000, a maximum of 500,000, and a minimum of 6,300. Bagheri's study reported an average WBC count of 45,000 [26], while Basabaeen's study reported an average of $92.86 \pm 75.43 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ [27].

The average percentage of lymphocytes in our study was $55.9 \pm 28.2\%$, and the average absolute number of peripheral blood lymphocytes was $27,628\pm 39,716/\mu\text{L}$. In Basabaeen's study, this figure was $82,230\pm 70,880/\mu\text{L}$ [27], and in Bagheri's study, the average number of patients' lymphocytes was $35,900/\mu\text{L}$ [26].

As shown, the results of our study concerning demographic parameters, such as age and gender, as well as the numbers of lymphocytes, anemia, and thrombocytopenia, align closely with findings from

other studies, particularly those conducted domestically. In the following section, we will discuss the analytical results of the study. Finally, we examined the relationship between the types of CLL (typical or atypical) and specific cell markers. In our study, we did not observe any significant correlation between the type of CLL and the six-cell markers we investigated. Notably, the average expression of CD22 and FMC7 was higher in the atypical CLL group. Conversely, the simultaneous expression of CD5/CD19 showed a higher average in the typical CLL group. A weak but significant correlation emerged between the type of CLL and the CD23 marker. This finding indicates that the average expression of CD23 in patients with typical CLL was higher than in patients with atypical CLL (p-value = 0.045), aligning with the results of Frater and his colleagues' study, where CD23 expression was significantly higher in patients with typical chronic lymphocytic leukemia (P=0.04) [23]. These findings shed light on the relationship between CLL types and specific cell markers, contributing to our understanding of the disease. As mentioned in Naeem's study, typical CLL is characterized by the expected proper expression of CD5, CD19, and CD23, moderate expression of CD20, and weak expression of CD22. Furthermore, CD79b and FMC7 are typically weak to negative in typical CLL cases [25]. This is why we classified patients with positive expression of FMC7, CD79b, CD22, and/or weak expression of CD5, CD19, and CD23, who were diagnosed with CLL, into the atypical group.

Conclusion

It is recommended that prospective assessments be conducted in individuals with chronic lymphocytic leukemia in order to assess variables like survival rates, treatment progression, and the clinical course of symptoms. These investigations can contribute to the clarification of the correlation between test results and prognosis.

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